

A Service Provider's Guide to Data Sharing Policies

These reference cards convey data sharing policy recommendations to be adopted by data and service providers within the EOSC-hub consortium.

Our recommendations contribute to the developing field of data sharing policies in the EOSC at large.

The Why | The What | The How

Why should you care about implementing data sharing policies? Three reasons.

For more details, consult the D2.8 and D2.9 deliverables via:
<https://bit.ly/2zDAANM>

DATA INTEGRITY & AUTHENTICITY

Information about provenance of scientific data is crucial to assess data integrity and authenticity.

EOSC-hub should consider the logging and tracking of scientific provenance data as an element of service integration design.

Good practice example: extending standard provenance modelling frameworks to include "workflow" structures¹.

Another EOSC-hub example is the PID-based provenance support through the integration with specific services like B2HANDLE as adopted by ENES².

CROSS-DOMAIN COLLABORATION

A wide variety of stakeholders broadens the engagement and facilitates cross-domain collaboration.

EOSC-hub should engage with a broader set of stakeholders, including social science and statistical data service providers, in supporting the design of a Europe-wide framework for research with sensitive data.

Examples of such engagements are EOSC-hub partners contributing to new projects like SoBigData++³.

TRUST AND CONFIDENCE

Adopting formal data sharing policies is an excellent step towards service accreditation. For providers of data and data services, external accreditation is becoming highly desirable, and sometimes essential, in building the necessary trust with important user communities, partner service providers, or both.

Whether the right path for you is CoreTrustSeal, ISO27001, FitSM, or even ISO16363, formalising your policies on data sharing is a key first step, and of itself a great way to build trust with your existing user base. Formal policies will also help you create networks with your partners to support emerging research data codes of conduct across shared user communities.

EOSC-hub and for example the CORBEL-project could mutually benefit from service accreditation⁴.

NOTES

1] P.Missier et al, D-PROV: extending the PROV provenance model with workflow structure. In: TaPP; 2013,
<https://bit.ly/3c5Dvml>

2] <https://bit.ly/37ZWTkc>

3] <https://bit.ly/2VhwJEx>

4] In the framework of the CORBEL project: EOSC-hub partner ECRIN has developed principles and recommendations
<https://bit.ly/2Z8PdZ2>